
74. Open clusters with Gaia

OPEN CLUSTERS are groups of several hundred stars, sites of star formation that were formed from the same giant molecular cloud, and therefore all of roughly the same age. They are still being formed in our Galaxy, at an estimated rate of one every few thousand years.

More than a thousand are known within our Galaxy, and many more are thought to exist. A few, such as the Hyades (at about 45 pc; see essay #20), the Pleiades (at about 130 pc; see essay #13), and the Alpha Persei cluster (at about 175 pc), are visible with the naked eye.

Open clusters are key objects in the study of stellar evolution. Because the cluster members are of similar age and chemical composition, their properties (such as distance, age, metallicity, extinction, and velocity) are more easily determined than they are for isolated stars.

ALTHOUGH LOOSELY BOUND by gravitational attraction when formed, open clusters slowly disperse as gas (and therefore mass) is stripped by the radiation pressure of their hot young stars. They are further disrupted by close encounters with other cluster stars, and other external structures, as they orbit the Galaxy.

They may survive as recognisable clumps for a few hundred million years, with the most massive surviving for a few billion. As stars slowly escape the gravitational field of the cluster, many will still be moving through space on a roughly similar path around the Galaxy, in what is known as a moving cluster or moving group.

WITH ITS SURVEY of all stars down to around 21 mag, its accurate star positions and space motions out to 1000 pc or more, and its unprecedented multi-epoch multi-colour photometry, Gaia is revolutionising their study. Quality positions allow cluster membership to be refined, space motions convey details of their dynamics and dispersion, and detailed photometry further contributes to classifying membership and chemistry.

With several hundred papers dealing with results from Gaia even by mid-2022, this can only serve as an incomplete introduction. A more detailed review of Gaia's contribution to date is given by Cantat-Gaudin (2022).

USING Data Release 2, Cantat-Gaudin et al. (2018) examined the extensive pre-Gaia open cluster catalogue compilations of Dias et al. (2002) and Kharchenko et al. (2013). They found that, from more than 3000 identified clusters, they could confirm only around 1200.

The explanation for this is of great importance for understanding star formation in our Galaxy (Kos et al. 2018): many previously suggested clusters are simply 'asterisms', stellar over-densities arising from strong extinction patterns mainly in the direction of the Galactic bulge. And excluding them results in a cluster age function in better agreement with theoretical models of their formation and dissolution (Anders et al. 2021).

As expected, Cantat-Gaudin et al. (2018) found that the youngest clusters are concentrated near the Galactic plane and trace the Galaxy's spiral arms, while older objects are more uniformly distributed, typically further from the plane, and at larger Galactocentric distances.

AMONGST OTHER statistical studies, Soubiran et al. (2018) used DR2 astrometry, including radial velocities, to study the positions and full space velocities for 861 clusters. They found that those with ages younger than 100 Myr have low vertical velocities and are, on average, within 100 pc of the Galactic plane. Clusters older than 1 Gyr span distances to the Galactic plane of up to 1 kpc, and with a vertical velocity dispersion of 14 km s^{-1} , are typical of the thin disk population.

Tarricq et al. (2021) determined Galactic orbits for 1382 clusters, showing that those younger than 30 Myr follow rather circular orbits, fully consistent with current models of star formation in which stars and clusters are formed on circular orbits near the Galactic mid-plane.

THE FACT THAT star clusters host coeval stars of different masses makes it straightforward in principle to estimate their ages from a colour-magnitude diagram combined with theoretical stellar evolution models. An analysis of the colour-magnitude diagrams of 269 clusters by Bossini et al. (2019) concluded that the uncertainty on the absolute age of clusters is now generally

dominated by uncertainties on stellar evolution models themselves, which will provide an important foundation for future theoretical modelling.

A number of other papers are now using the Gaia data to yield simultaneous estimates of cluster properties such as distance, extinction, total mass, age, and metallicity (e.g. Kounkel et al. 2020; Perren et al. 2020).

THE PHYSICAL PROCESS driving the formation and persistence of spiral arms, in our Galaxy and beyond, remains a matter of debate – whether they are global and stationary, or local features of a more transient nature. Here, Gaia is also providing new insights.

Castro-Ginard et al. (2021) used EDR3 data to examine the birthplaces of young open clusters in the Perseus, local, Sagittarius, and Scutum spiral arms, to trace the evolution of the different spiral structures. Finding different pattern speeds for the different arms, they argued that their results question classical density waves as the main drivers for Galaxy’s spiral structure, being in better agreement with models favouring transient features.

The detailed structure of the various spiral arms, inferred from the spatial distribution of young clusters, is likely to provide other constraints on spiral arm models. Amongst these are studies of the Perseus arm (Cantat-Gaudin et al. 2019); the local arm (Xu et al. 2021); the Cepheus spur (Pantaleoni et al. 2021); and the Sagittarius spur (Kuhn et al. 2021).

MANY PAPERS have taken up the challenge of identifying *new* open clusters in DR2 and EDR3, frequently using the accurate proper motions to identify groups of stars that are kinematically coherent, even if they may be spatially sparse. These searches are making use of a variety of advanced clustering algorithms.

Meanwhile, Koposov et al. (2017) discovered two massive disk clusters, which they named Gaia 1 and Gaia 2. At least the former appears to be a massive and luminous open cluster, rather than a low-mass globular cluster (Koch et al., 2018).

Amongst other reported discoveries, Cantat-Gaudin et al. (2018) claimed 60 new open clusters; Castro-Ginard et al. (2018) identified 31; Cantat-Gaudin et al. (2019) found 41 in the Perseus arm; Castro-Ginard et al. (2019) discovered 53 towards the Galactic anti-centre; Sim et al. (2019) found 207; He et al. (2021) found 74 clusters with a nearest-neighbour approach; Hunt & Refert (2021) reported 41; while in all-sky supercomputer-based searches, Castro-Ginard et al. (2020) discovered 582 clusters in DR2, and Castro-Ginard et al. (2022) found a further 664 in EDR3.

But there is likely no clear answer as to how many new clusters will be found with the Gaia data, for at the sparsest levels even pairs of comoving stars may point to long-disrupted clusters (e.g. Kamdar et al. 2019).

THE DYNAMICAL EVOLUTION of open clusters can be witnessed as stars escaping from the cluster, preferentially through their Lagrange points L1 and L2, and leading to the formation of tidal tails.

These are seen most prominently in the Hyades cluster (my essay #20). But they are also now evident in Praesepe (Röser & Schilbach, 2019); Ruprecht 147 (Yeh et al., 2019); M67 (Carrera et al., 2019); Coma Ber (Tang et al., 2019); Czernik 3 (Sharma et al., 2020); Blanco 1 (Zhang et al., 2020); IC 4756 (Ye et al., 2021); and NGC 752 (Bhattacharya et al., 2021). In the Gaia-discovered ‘colliding’ clusters IC 4665 and Collinder 350, each is perhaps driving the other’s tidal disruption (Piatti & Malhan, 2021).

Other evidence of their dynamical evolution are ‘runaway’ stars, in which high proper motions pinpoint stars which have been hurled out of their natal cluster via a binary–supernova interaction, or through the disruption of single–binary or binary–binary systems.

THE DETAILED colour–magnitude diagrams of open (as well as globular) clusters also allow the identification of stars in unusual stages of stellar evolution. Gaia results are starting to appear on blue straggler stars, of uncertain origin but manifested as stars both brighter and bluer than the cluster’s main-sequence turnoff.

And many new results are emerging on white dwarf in clusters, as well as on particular variability types such as young Delta Scuti stars and Cepheid variables.

FURTHER COMPLICATING an already involved picture are the groupings of young, luminous O- and B-type stars, the OB associations. Models in which OB associations are formed from the expansion of previously compact clusters are no longer favoured. Indeed, as summarised in my essay #18 on ‘The Origin of OB Associations’, the Gaia results are more consistent with hierarchical star formation, in which stars are formed across a continuous density distribution throughout molecular clouds, rather than exclusively within clusters, and in which OB associations are formed *in situ* as relatively large-scale and gravitationally-unbound structures.

While the distinction between clusters and associations therefore becomes somewhat arbitrary, I will not attempt to touch on the extensive Gaia literature on associations here. And other spatial features are being reported from the Gaia data, amongst them structures referred to as strings or filaments (Kounkel & Covey, 2019); rings (Cantat-Gaudin et al., 2019); snakes (Tian 2020; Wang et al. 2022); and pearls (Coronado et al., 2022).

AS CONCLUDED by Cantat-Gaudin (2022) in his recent review: ‘*The Gaia data have unlocked a deluge of new results related to many astronomical topics and transformed our ability to study star clusters and stellar structures in the Milky Way.*’